

The Role of Sulfur, Tryptophan Acid, and Methyl Jasmonate in Vegetative Growth, Quality Indicators, and Total Yield of Lettuce Plants

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Abstract:

The experiment was conducted in one of the agricultural fields of the College of Agriculture – University of Karbala during the agricultural growing season 2023-2024. The factorial experiment was designed according to the Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three factors: the first factor was the addition of agricultural sulfur at three levels (0, 15, and 25 kg ha⁻¹), the second factor was spraying the amino acid tryptophan at three levels (0, 100, and 200 mg L⁻¹), and the third factor was spraying methyl jasmonate at three levels (0, 75, and 150 mg L⁻¹). The Least Significant Differences Test (L.S.D) was used to compare the means at a

probability level of 0.05 for the growth and yield of lettuce plants (*Lactuca sativa* L.). The results indicated that the vegetative growth indicators (plant height, stem diameter, total number of leaves, and dry weight of the plant) increased in value when the factors were combined (addition of sulfur at 25 kg ha⁻¹ + spraying tryptophan at 200 mg L⁻¹ + spraying methyl jasmonate at 100 mg L⁻¹). The recorded values were (35.84 cm plant⁻¹, 3.89 cm plant⁻¹, 44.36 leaves plant⁻¹, and 48.30 g plant⁻¹) respectively. In contrast, the treatment sprayed with distilled water only gave the lowest results (27.96 cm plant⁻¹, 2.65 cm plant⁻¹, 26.71 leaves plant⁻¹, and 25.18 g plant⁻¹) respectively. In addition, The results showed that the chemical indicators of the plant increased when the factors were combined (addition of sulfur at 25 kg ha⁻¹ + spraying tryptophan at 200 mg L⁻¹ + spraying methyl jasmonate at 100 mg L⁻¹), with total soluble carbohydrates content in leaves (29.15 mg g⁻¹ dry weight plant⁻¹), the percentage of fiber in leaves (37.06%), nitrate concentration in leaves (797.41 mg kg⁻¹), and oil estimation (3.46%). In contrast, the control treatment recorded the lowest values, with 18.06 mg g⁻¹ dry weight plant⁻¹, 15.27%, 1824.03 mg kg⁻¹, and 1.03%, respectively. The combination of the three factors at the levels (sulfur at 25 kg ha⁻¹ + tryptophan at 200 mg L⁻¹ + and methyl jasmonate at 100 mg L⁻¹) resulted in the highest values in the studied yield indicators of the plant (average marketable head weight (were 753.42 g per plant), and total yield (33.904 tons ha⁻¹). In contrast, the control treatment, where plants were only sprayed with distilled water, gave the lowest results, with 361.66 g per plant and 16.275 tons per hectare, respectively.

Keywords: Sulfur, Tryptophan, Methyl Jasmonate, Lettuce, Yield Growth.

Introduction

Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) is considered a very important vegetable winter crop in Iraq and

worldwide. It belongs to the composite family (Borass et al., 2006). It belongs to the composite family (Borass et al., 2006). Lettuce which are eaten fresh has been considered one of the most

important salad crops due to its high nutritional value. Lettuce is rich in niacin and calcium and moderately content iron, vitamin A, and riboflavin. It also contains some organic acids such as citric acid (Khalil, 2004).

Sulfur is required for the formation of S-S bonds in the structure of amino acids and is involved to a great extent in vitamins and ferredoxin formation. It is also responsible for powering electron transport chain components with strong reducing power under light reactions of photosynthesis. Further, sulfur helps in giving taste and flavor to plant foods, with many vegetables being characterized by this mineral. In the composition of plants, it is involved in most nonessential compounds that help in creating defensive mechanisms against agricultural pests (Josseph et al., 2013). In addition, it plays an important role in supporting plant growth and development processes, thereby increasing overall yields (Kahar and Ahmed, 2015). The precursor of IAA biosynthesis is tryptophan or an intermediate, indole-3-glycerol phosphate. There are four biosynthetic pathways of IAA in plants, whereas three of them are related to the amino acid tryptophan. These include the IPyA pathway, the TAM pathway, and the IAN pathway. More importantly, the diversity of these biosynthetic pathways for IAA from tryptophan underscores the very importance of this hormone and its precursor in the growth and development of plants (Mano and Nemoto, 2012).

Methyl jasmonate (MeJA) is characterized by a specific aromatic odor, and as a derivative of jasmonate, it is classified among growth hormones that have a positive influence on the growth and development of plants. Some studies

have determined the influence of MeJA on the growth and flowering of horticultural plants; it induces several physiological changes in the plant tissues and causes morphological alterations in the plants themselves (Luo et al., 2019). Additionally, the group of jasmonate triggers a wide range of physiological activities in plants, for example, growth, development, and the ability to tolerate biotic stress (Amran and Abbass, 2024).

The nutritional and medicinal importance of lettuce is high, creating the necessity to explore modern agronomic methods to increase its vegetative yield and enhance its active compounds. The present study aimed to investigate the effect of sulfur, tryptophan acid, and methyl jasmonate on the growth indicators, yield, and some active compounds of lettuce. It also sought to identify the best interactions between the experimental factors and their qualitative and quantitative effects on the studied indicators.

Material and Methods

The study was carried out in one of the fields belonging to the College of Agriculture, University of Karbala, during the agricultural season 2023-2024. Soil samples were collected from the field before planting, randomly, from various places and at different depths ranging from 0-30 cm. The soil samples were then air-dried, dried and thickness was 2 mm. The soil physicochemical analysis was carried out in the laboratory of the University of Agriculture, Al-Qasim Al-Khadra University, Department of Soil and Water.

Table 1. Some Physical and Chemical Pre-Planting Soil Tests

Soil properties					
Soil Texture	Sand (g kg ⁻¹)	Silt (g kg ⁻¹)	Clay (g kg ⁻¹)	pH	EC
Sandy Loam	856	30	13	7.6	2.7

The test plot was prepared by removing growing weeds, after which the soil was prepared, leveled, surface smooth uniformly and consistently. The soil was then sterilized with the fungicide

Ridomil. The land was divided into three replicates, each comprising 27 experimental units. Each experimental unit was represented by three drip irrigation pipes, covering an area of 1

m² and containing 9 plants. A distance of 0.5 m was left between the experimental units, and the same distance was maintained between the replicates to serve as a buffer to prevent mixing of treatments. All cultivation, irrigation, weeding, and pest control operations were carried out as recommended.

Experimental Treatments

The experiment included three factors as follows:

- 1. First Factor:** Addition of pure agricultural sulfur of Iraqi origin, where sulfur constitutes 100%. The sulfur was added to the soil before planting and after dividing the experimental units at three levels: 0, 15, and 25 kg ha⁻¹, labeled as S0, S1, and S2, respectively.
- 2. Second Factor:** Spraying the amino acid tryptophan on the foliage at two intervals with concentrations of 0, 100, and 200 mg L⁻¹, labeled as t0, t1, and t2, respectively. (The spraying was conducted at sunset to avoid direct sunlight and to increase the efficiency of amino acid absorption by the plants.)
- 3. Third Factor:** Spraying methyl jasmonate on the foliage at two intervals with concentrations of 0, 75, and 150 mg L⁻¹, labeled as m0, m1, and m2, respectively. The plants were sprayed early in the morning until thoroughly wet. Tryptophan was sprayed first, and after 48 hours, the plants were sprayed with methyl jasmonate. The first spray was done 25 days after transplanting in the permanent field, the second spray was done two weeks after the first spray, and the third spray was done two weeks after the second spray. The control treatment was sprayed with distilled water only.

Experimental Design

The experiment was conducted as a factorial experiment with three factors (3×3×3) using a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). It comprised 27 experimental units with three replicates, totaling 81 experimental units. Comparison between means was performed using the Least Significant Differences (LSD) Test at a 0.05% probability level (Al-Rawi and Khalaf Allah, 2000). To determine significant differences between the means, the statistical

software Genstat v.12 was used, following the method described by Al-Asadi (2019).

Studied Indicators

1. Vegetative Growth Indicators:

Five plants were randomly selected from each experimental unit (15 plants per treatment) 106 days after planting for vegetative measurements, which included the following:

- 1. Plant Height (cm plant⁻¹):** Plant height was measured at the horticultural maturity stage using a metric tape measure from the soil-plant contact area to the top of the selected plants. A ruler was placed at the top of the plant to accurately determine the height with the tape measure for all experimental units.
- 2. Stem Diameter (cm plant⁻¹):** Stem diameter was measured using a Vernier caliper at a height of 1 cm from the lower third of the plant (crown area) of the randomly selected plants from the experimental units at the horticultural maturity stage.
- 3. Total Number of Leaves (leaf plant⁻¹):** The total number of leaves per plant was counted, excluding very small leaves at the growing tip of the stem that were 1 cm long.
- 4. Dry Weight of the Plant (g plant⁻¹):** Dry weight was determined at a temperature of 70°C for 72 hours until the weight stabilized.

Chemical Indicators of the Plant

Total Soluble Carbohydrates Content in Leaves (mg g⁻¹ dry weight/plant)

The amount of carbohydrates in the leaves per plant for each treatment was estimated by grinding 100 mg of the dried ground sample with 10 ml of distilled water. The extract was separated using a centrifuge at a speed of 1500 rpm. Then, 1 ml of the extract was taken and mixed with 1 ml of 5% phenol reagent and 5 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). The procedure followed a published method (Herbert et al., 1971) to measure glucose levels. A mixture was allowed to cool for 25 minutes and light absorption was measured at 490 nm using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan). To get a reference, glucose of known

concentrations (50, 100, 150, 200 milligrams per liter) was poured into water. Then, 1 milliliter of each solution was mixed with a phenol solution and sulfuric acid. Finally, the light absorption of all solutions was measured at 490 nanometers, and the data was recorded.

Percentage of Fibers in Leaves (%)

Sample of 2.5 g leaves, ground, were boiled for half an hour in each treatment with 0.25 ml sulfuric acid. The mixture was filtered after boiling, and the residue was dried in an electric oven at 100°C. After drying, the samples were weighed, and then the dry matter (fibers) was burned in a furnace at a temperature of 600°C. The percentage fiber was obtained by the formula: (A.O.A.C, 1980)

$$\text{Fibers \%} = \frac{\text{Weight after drying at } 100^{\circ}\text{C} - \text{Weight after burning at } 600^{\circ}\text{C}}{\text{Weight of dry matter}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Nitrate Concentration in Leaves (mg kg⁻¹)

Nitrate was determined according to Cataldo et al. 1975. Sample of 0.1 g ground floral discs were taken, and placed in a test tube with 10 ml of distilled water, hand shaken and incubated at a temperature of 45°C for 60 minutes. It was shaken again on a horizontal shaker for 15 minutes. It was then centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 minutes, after which a sample of the supernatant was withdrawn by pipetting 0.2 mL and introduced into a flask where 0.8 mL of 5% W/V salicylic acid-sulfuric acid (SA-H₂SO₄) was added. After 20 minutes, 19 ml of 2 M NaOH was added to the flask. A standard nitrate solution was prepared from potassium nitrate (KNO₃). A sample from this solution was read using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 410 nm, and the readings were calibrated against the standard curve.

Oil Content Estimation

Oil content was estimated using the Soxhlet apparatus according to the method described in A.O.A.C, 1980, and Harborne (1973). A special glass flask for the Soxhlet apparatus was weighed to the nearest fourth decimal place. Then, 5 g of the plant sample with known moisture content was taken, wrapped in filter paper, and placed in a porous container specific to the apparatus to prevent the sample from escaping into the receiving flask. The receiving flask was filled with 250 ml of petroleum ether (this amount can vary). The flask containing the solvent was

heated on a heat source. The solvent condensed and, upon entering the condenser, returned to the flask, passing through the sample and carrying the dissolved oil with it. This process continued for approximately 7 hours. After the solvent was evaporated, the flask was weighed again, and the oil percentage was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Oil percentage} = \frac{\text{weight of fat}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Yield Indicators

Average Marketable Head Weight (g)

The average weight of the marketable head was calculated after removing the roots and non-marketable outer leaves.

Total Yield (ton ha⁻¹):

The yield per experimental unit was calculated and then scaled to a hectare using the following equation:

$$\text{Total Yield (ton per ha)} = \frac{\text{Yield of the experimental unit}}{\text{Area of the experimental unit m}^2} \times 10000 \text{ m}^2 \quad (3)$$

Results

Vegetative Growth Indicators

Tables 1 and 2 show that sulfur fertilization has a significant effect on vegetative growth indicators at a concentration of 25 kg ha⁻¹. The highest results were recorded for plant height, stem diameter, total number of leaves, and dry weight of the plant, reaching (34.79 cm plant⁻¹, 3.49 cm plant⁻¹, 39.92 leaves plant⁻¹, and 41.77 g plant⁻¹) respectively, compared to the lowest

rates in the control treatment (29.58 cm plant⁻¹, 2.92 cm plant⁻¹, 28.41 leaves plant⁻¹, and 27.92 g plant⁻¹) respectively. The results indicated that spraying tryptophan has a significant effect on vegetative growth indicators, with the 200 mg L⁻¹ treatment recording the highest results in all studied vegetative indicators. Similarly, spraying methyl jasmonate had a significant effect at a concentration of 150 mg L⁻¹, with the highest results recorded for the studied vegetative indicators compared to the lowest rates recorded in the control treatment.

Table 1. The Role of Sulfur, Tryptophan, and Jasmonate in Plant Height and Stem Diameter

Sulfur S	Tryptophan T	Plant height (cm plant ⁻¹)				Stem diameter (cm plant ⁻¹)				
		Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T	Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T	
		M0	M1	M2		M0	M1	M2		
S0	T0	27.96	28.48	29.05	28.49	2.65	2.86	2.91	2.80	
	T1	28.91	29.73	30.89	29.84	2.89	2.95	2.99	2.94	
	T2	30.26	30.08	30.90	30.41	2.98	3.02	3.06	3.02	
S1	T0	30.54	31.41	32.28	31.41	3.03	3.11	3.15	3.09	
	T1	31.76	32.66	33.30	32.57	3.13	3.18	3.25	3.18	
	T2	32.99	34.85	34.97	34.27	3.24	3.46	3.50	3.40	
S2	T0	33.75	34.01	34.26	34.00	3.28	3.30	3.31	3.29	
	T1	34.47	35.11	35.39	34.99	3.36	3.57	3.62	3.51	
	T2	34.75	35.84	35.62	35.40	3.38	3.89	3.74	3.67	
Mean (M)		31.71	32.46	32.96		3.10	3.26	3.28		
L.S.D. 0.05		M = S*T*M = 1.34			S*T = 0.77	M = 0.11		S*T*M = 0.35		
S*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean S	M0	M1	M2	Mean S	
S*M		S0	29.04	29.43	30.28	29.58	2.84	2.94	2.98	2.92
S*M		S1	31.76	32.97	32.51	32.41	3.13	3.25	3.30	3.22
S*M		S2	34.32	34.98	35.09	34.79	3.34	3.58	3.55	3.49
L.S.D. 0.05		S*M = 0.77			S = 0.44	S*M = 0.20			S = 0.11	
T*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean T	M0	M1	M2	Mean	
T*M		T0	30.75	31.30	32.10	31.38	2.98	3.09	3.12	3.06
T*M		T1	31.71	32.50	33.19	32.46	3.13	3.23	3.28	3.21
T*M		T2	32.66	33.59	33.83	33.36	3.20	3.45	3.43	3.36
L.S.D. 0.05		T*M = 0.77			T = 0.44	T*M = 0.20			T = 0.11	

Table 2. The Role of Sulfur, Tryptophan, and Jasmonate in Leaf Number and Plant Dry Weight

Sulfur S	Tryptophan T	Total leaf number (leaf plant ⁻¹)				Plant dry weight (gm plant ⁻¹)			
		Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T	Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T
		M0	M1	M2		M0	M1	M2	
S0	T0	26.71	28.08	28.25	27.68	25.18	26.93	27.42	26.51
	T1	28.17	28.43	29.06	28.55	26.99	27.86	28.84	27.89
	T2	28.50	29.18	29.34	29.00	28.60	29.30	30.25	29.38
S1	T0	29.22	30.92	32.48	30.87	29.77	30.40	31.08	30.41
	T1	31.16	32.80	34.38	32.78	30.79	32.56	34.19	32.51
	T2	33.19	39.28	40.46	37.64	33.32	42.70	44.01	40.01
S2	T0	35.12	35.53	36.85	35.83	35.08	36.60	37.11	36.26
	T1	38.10	42.97	43.51	41.52	39.43	45.89	46.24	43.85
	T2	38.82	44.36	44.07	42.41	40.15	48.30	47.15	45.20

Mean (M)		32.11	34.61	35.37		32.14	35.61	36.25		
L.S.D. 0.05	M =	S*T*M = 0.86			S*T =050	M =0.30	S*T*M = 0.91		S*T	
S*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean S	M0	M1	M2	Mea	
S*M	S0	27.79	28.56	28.88	28.41	26.92	28.03	28.83	27.92	
	S1	31.19	34.33	35.77	33.76	31.29	35.22	36.42	34.31	
	S2	37.34	40.95	41.47	39.92	38.22	43.59	43.50	41.77	
L.S.D. 0.05		S*M =0.50			S =0.28	S*M =0.53			S	
T*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean T	M0	M1	M2	Mea	
	T*M	T0	30.35	31.51	32.52	31.46	30.01	31.31	31.87	31.06
		T1	32.47	34.73	35.65	34.28	32.40	35.27	36.42	34.69
		T2	33.50	37.60	37.96	36.35	34.02	40.10	40.47	38.19
	L.S.D. 0.05		T*M =0.50			T=0.28	T*M =0.53			T

Chemical Indicators of the Plant

Tables 3 and 4 show that sulfur fertilization has a significant effect on chemical growth indicators at a concentration of 25 kg ha⁻¹. The highest results were recorded for total soluble carbohydrates content in leaves, percentage of fibers in leaves, nitrate concentration in leaves, and oil content, reaching (26.83 mg g⁻¹ dry weight plant⁻¹, 32.34%, 855.47 mg kg⁻¹, and 3.02%) respectively, compared to the lowest rates in the control treatment (20.42 mg g⁻¹ dry weight plant⁻¹, 18.15%, 1230.36 mg kg⁻¹, and 1.79%) respectively. The results revealed that spraying tryptophan has a significant effect on the studied chemical indicators, with the 200 mg L⁻¹ treatment recording the highest results in all

chemical growth indicators. Similarly, spraying methyl jasmonate had a significant effect at a concentration of 150 mg L⁻¹, with the highest results recorded for the studied indicators compared to the lowest rates recorded in the control treatment. In addition, Results indicate that three-way interaction S₂T₂M₁ significantly outperformed with the highest results in the indicators of total soluble carbohydrates content in leaves, percentage of fibers in leaves, nitrate concentration in leaves, and oil content, at (29.15 mg g⁻¹ dry weight plant⁻¹, 37.06%, 797.41 mg kg⁻¹, and 3.46%) respectively, compared to the lowest rates recorded in the control treatment, (18.06 mg g⁻¹ dry weight plant⁻¹, 15.27%, 1824.03 mg kg⁻¹, and 1.03%) respectively.

Table 3. The Role of Sulfur, Tryptophan, and Jasmonate in Total Soluble Carbohydrate and Fiber%

Sulfur S	Tryptophan T	Total soluble carbohydrate mg g ⁻¹ dry weight plant ⁻¹				Fiber % in leaves			
		Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T	Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T
		M0	M1	M2		M0	M1	M2	
S0	T0	18.06	19.72	20.23	19.33	15.27	16.91	17.45	16.54
	T1	19.91	20.50	21.07	20.49	17.13	17.88	19.16	18.05
	T2	20.84	21.41	22.14	21.46	18.67	19.59	21.38	19.88
S1	T0	21.83	22.39	23.00	22.40	20.26	22.70	24.55	22.50
	T1	22.70	23.54	24.33	23.52	23.81	24.39	26.74	24.98
	T2	23.92	26.96	27.08	25.98	25.07	32.85	33.90	30.60
S2	T0	24.61	24.99	25.68	25.09	27.82	28.65	29.40	28.62
	T1	25.84	27.52	28.40	27.25	30.09	34.16	35.70	33.31
	T2	26.63	29.15	28.73	28.17	31.84	37.06	36.43	35.11
Mean (M)		22.70	24.02	24.51		23.32	26.02	27.19	
L.S.D. 0.05	M =	S*T*M = 0.96			S*T =0.55	M =0.29	S*T*M = 0.87		S*T
S*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean S	M0	M1	M2	Mean S
S*M	S0	19.60	20.54	21.14	20.42	17.02	18.12	19.33	18.15
	S1	22.81	24.29	24.80	23.96	23.04	26.64	28.39	26.02
	S2	25.69	27.22	27.60	26.83	29.91	33.29	33.84	32.34
L.S.D. 0.05		S*M =0.55			S =0.32	S*M =0.50			S =0.29

T*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean T	M0	M1	M2	Mean
T*M	T0	21.50	22.36	22.97	22.27	21.87	22.75	23.80	22.80
	T1	22.81	23.85	24.60	23.75	23.67	25.47	27.20	25.44
	T2	23.79	25.84	25.98	25.20	25.19	29.83	30.57	28.53
L.S.D. 0.05		T*M=0.55			T=0.32	T*M=0.50			T

Table 4. The Role of Sulfur, Tryptophan, and Jasmonate in Nitrate and Oil%

Sulfur S	Tryptophan T	Nitrate Concentration in Leaves (mg kg ⁻¹)				Oil %			
		Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T	Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T
		M0	M1	M2		M0	M1	M2	
S0	T0	1824.03	1392.25	1251.44	1489.24	1.03	1.67	1.79	1.49
	T1	1308.90	1176.26	1065.08	1183.41	1.74	1.86	1.94	1.84
	T2	1113.37	1019.82	922.18	1041.79	1.91	1.99	2.19	2.03
S1	T0	993.72	907.53	871.81	924.35	2.08	2.26	2.37	2.23
	T1	894.05	958.14	930.80	927.66	2.30	2.46	2.61	2.45
	T2	949.92	857.51	848.70	885.25	2.55	2.98	3.07	2.86
S2	T0	915.17	896.04	881.85	897.93	2.68	2.73	2.78	2.73
	T1	872.62	840.72	828.11	847.15	2.84	3.15	3.26	3.08
	T2	863.08	797.41	804.29	821.58	2.92	3.46	3.38	3.25
Mean (M)		1081.65	982.85	933.82		2.22	2.50	2.36	
L.S.D. 0.05		M = S*T*M = 57.09			S*T	M =0.16	S*T*M = 0.50		S*T
S*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean S	M0	M1	M2	Mean S
S*M	S0	1415.43	1196.11	1079.56	1230.36	1.56	1.84	1.97	1.79
	S1	945.89	907.72	883.77	912.46	2.31	2.56	2.68	2.51
	S2	883.62	844.72	838.08	855.47	2.81	3.11	3.14	3.02
L.S.D. 0.05		S*M =32.96			S =19.03	S*M =0.29			S =0.16
T*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean T	M0	M1	M2	Mean
T*M	T0	1244.30	1065.27	1001.70	1103.75	1.93	2.22	2.31	2.15
	T1	1025.19	991.71	941.33	986.07	2.29	2.49	2.60	2.46
	T2	975.45	891.58	858.39	908.47	2.46	2.81	2.88	2.71
L.S.D. 0.05		T*M =32.96			T=19.03	T*M =0.29			T

Plant Yield Indicators

Table 5 shows that sulfur fertilization has a significant effect on yield indicators at a concentration of 25 kg ha⁻¹. The highest results were recorded for average head weight (g plant⁻¹) and total plant yield (ton ha⁻¹), at (700.11 g plant⁻¹ and 31.814 ton ha⁻¹) respectively, compared to the lowest rates in the control treatment at (491.23 g plant⁻¹ and 23.103 ton ha⁻¹) respectively.

The result indicates that spraying tryptophan has a significant effect on the studied yield indicators, with the 200 mg L⁻¹ treatment recording the highest results in all plant yield

indicators. Similarly, spraying methyl jasmonate had a significant effect at a concentration of 150 mg L⁻¹, with the highest results recorded for the studied indicators compared to the lowest rates recorded in the control treatment. Results indicate that three-way interaction S₂T₂M₁ significantly outperformed with the highest results in the indicators of average head weight (g plant⁻¹) and total plant yield (ton ha⁻¹), at (753.42 g plant⁻¹ and 33.904 ton ha⁻¹) respectively, compared to the lowest rates recorded in the control treatment, which were (361.66 g plant⁻¹ and 16.275 ton ha⁻¹) respectively.

Table 5 The Role of Sulfur, Tryptophan Acid, and Methyl Jasmonate in Yield Indicators (Average Head Weight and Total Yield) of Lettuce

Sulfur S	Tryptophan T	Average Head Weight (g plant ⁻¹)				Total Yield (ton ha ⁻¹)			
		Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T	Methyl Jasmonate M			S * T
		M0	M1	M2		M0	M1	M2	
S0	T0	361.66	482.18	518.46	454.10	16.275	21.698	23.330	20.434
	T1	497.75	526.26	550.03	524.68	22.399	23.681	24.750	23.610
	T2	539.91	363.34	581.52	494.92	24.296	25.350	26.168	25.271
S1	T0	574.39	595.07	620.14	596.53	25.847	26.778	27.907	26.844
	T1	608.20	627.28	649.13	628.20	27.369	28.228	29.211	28.269
	T2	633.26	701.41	718.95	684.54	28.496	31.563	32.352	30.803
S2	T0	661.91	667.00	679.85	669.58	29.785	30.015	30.593	30.131
	T1	686.97	730.46	738.77	718.73	30.914	32.870	33.244	32.342
	T2	697.68	753.42	746.85	732.65	31.396	33.904	33.608	32.969
Mean (M)		584.63	605.15	644.86		26.308	28.231	29.018	
L.S.D. 0.05		M =			S*T*M = 11.13	S*T = 6.42	M = 0.50	S*T*M = 1.50	S*T
S*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean S	M0	M1	M2	Mean S
S*M	S0	466.44	457.26	550.00	491.23	20.990	23.576	24.744	23.103
	S1	605.28	641.25	662.74	636.42	27.237	28.856	29.823	28.638
	S2	682.18	696.34	721.82	700.11	30.698	32.263	32.481	31.814
L.S.D. 0.05		S*M = 6.42			S = 3.71	S*M = 0.86			S = 0.50
T*M		M0	M1	M2	Mean T	M0	M1	M2	Mean
T*M	T0	532.65	581.41	606.15	573.40	23.969	26.163	27.276	25.802
	T1	597.64	628.00	645.97	623.87	26.894	28.259	29.068	28.073
	T2	623.61	606.05	682.44	637.36	28.062	30.272	30.709	29.681
L.S.D. 0.05		T*M = 6.42			T = 3.71	T*M = 0.86			T

Discussion

The results show that the addition of sulfur to the soil caused a decrease in soil pH, which led to an increase in the activity and proliferation of beneficial microorganisms, as they are activated in acidic environments. The absorbed sulfates are reduced within the plant to SH groups, which are essential for activating oxidation-reduction processes. Sulfur is also involved in the formation of the coenzyme CoASH and vitamins Biotin and Thiamine, which play important roles in the production of some metabolic compounds necessary for the formation of proteins that constitute enzymes. These enzymes are hormonally regulated, and their patterns influence early development (Sharivastava et al., 2000), increasing the investigated plant growth parameters.

It was observed that the indicators of vegetative growth studied increased with the application of the amino acid tryptophan. This may be due to its role as a precursor for the biosynthesis of IAA (Indole-3-Acetic Acid). There are four pathways for IAA synthesis in plants, three of which

depend on the amino acid tryptophan. The significant impact of this hormone and its precursor on plant growth and development is evident from the multiple biosynthetic pathways for IAA. This finding aligns with the results reported by Orabi *et al.* (2014).

Spraying with methyl jasmonate was found to have a significant impact, leading to an increase in the concentration of essential elements such as nitrogen (N) and potassium (K), which are crucial for cell construction and enhancing carbon assimilation activity. This boost in activity improves the plant's water retention capacity, resulting in an increase in the number of cells and, subsequently, in vegetative growth indicators. Moreover, methyl jasmonate plays a vital role in protecting the plant and promoting growth by stimulating carbon assimilation and increasing pigment levels. This enhancement improves the permeability of membranes to essential nutrients, thereby improving vegetative growth indicators and positively impacting productivity. The application of methyl jasmonate has been shown to increase physiological processes, especially

photosynthesis, which significantly regulates numerous vital processes within the plant (Ziosi *et al.*, 2009).

The increase in chemical indicators can be attributed to sulfur as per the above tables. This is because, with the addition of sulfur, it decreases soil pH levels. The core elements in the soil are iron and magnesium. If these nutrients are all present in optimal concentrations with increased availability due to a decrease in soil pH, then their concentration availability will be sufficiently increased for plant absorption, which is very vital for chlorophyll molecule construction. As to sulfur, in its interaction with nitrogen, it increases the nucleic acid synthesis followed by the chlorophyll and proteins, which subsequently increases the level of photosynthetic efficiency in the process of the resultant carbohydrates production (Assimakopoulou, 2006).

The superiority of tryptophan application in increasing the levels of internal growth regulators, which act as sinks for mineral elements and nutrients, aligns with the findings reported by Yassen *et al.* (2010).

The results from all tables show that there is significant influence by Methyl Jasmonate on the chemical indicators of the study in treatments sprayed with the growth regulator. Use of Methyl Jasmonate will minimize stomatal resistance, maximize stomatal conductance and chlorophyll concentration as well as improve the rate of photosynthesis, which alleviates the impacts of stress. This finding confirms Rezaei *et al.* Besides, superiority of tryptophan application in elevating contents of internal growth regulators and as a sink of mineral elements, and nutrients, it agrees with the findings by Yassen *et al.*, 2010.

The results from adding sulfur to the soil, spraying tryptophan, and methyl jasmonate indicate these treatments positively impact lettuce yield. This increase is due to improved vegetative growth, enhanced nutrient availability, and increased photosynthesis, leading to more carbohydrates, nutrients, leaves, and higher productivity.

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